

MAQASID AL-SHARI'AH IN ISLAMIC FINANCE: AN OVERVIEW

Mirza Vejzagic*

Edib Smolo**

ABSTRACT

Islam is a divine revelation for all people and the Prophet (s.a.w.s.) has been sent as compassion to Muslims as well as all humanity. It embraces whole life including economic and financial aspects that contain paths which lead to a social order along with social justice and economic prosperity. This conception is deeply adorned in the objectives of *Shari'ah*, also known as *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*. Islamic finance, as a part of this extraordinary conception, could be relatively classified in three main areas: Islamic banking, capital markets and insurance (*takaful*). *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* is considered to be the cornerstone or the guiding principle of Islamic finance. It applies to everything: laws, conduct, opinions, products, transactions, activities, and services. It outlines the objectives and wisdom (*hikmah*) as prescribed by *Shari'ah* in all its rulings to protect and preserve the benefits and interests (*maslahah*) of society. Furthermore, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* facilitate the needs of human being, ensure the wealth is circulated among as many as possible in a fair way, avoid dispute and ensure stability, promote *maslahah* and avoid harm, promote transparency and accountability and uphold and promote justice in acquiring wealth. In facing or solving current issues in the aspects of social, economics, politics and finance, the application of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* is an important element that needs to be incorporated by all Muslims. In addition, there should be continuous emphasize on the importance of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in all Islamic finance fields. It must be underlined through recommendation to all relevant financial bodies to promote these gracious *Shari'ah* objectives in the markets and provide application for them correspondingly in the relevant industries for better future of Islamic finance.

Keywords: *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*, Islamic Banking, Islamic Capital Markets (*Sukuk*), *Takaful*

* Mirza Vejzagic is a Ph.D. candidate at International Centre for Education in Islamic Finance (INCEIF), Malaysia. He can be contacted at mirza_vejzagic@yahoo.com.

** Corresponding author – Edib Smolo is a Ph.D. candidate at INCEIF andÉ a researcher at International Shari'ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance (ISRA). He can be contacted at edib@isra.my or hfz.edib@gmail.com.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Islamic finance industry has grown both geographically and in product affluence although it has been continuously facing the complex conditions in the universal financial markets and the global uncertainties. It was founded as a tiny industry in the late 1960s.¹ Its development has been increasing ever since, in terms of the number of states in which it operates, as well as the field of disciplines of finance in which it is performing. Islamic finance distinguishes itself from conventional counterpart in its professed compliance with principles of Islamic law, or *Shari'ah*. In addition, contemporary literature emphasize that Islamic finance diverges considerably from conventional not merely based on the background it observes in businesses performance, but also in the way in which noble principles steer Islamic finance's entire procedures and position. The principles which are embraced within the realm of *Shari'ah* are uttered not only in the details of its transactions but in the extent of its role in implementing the *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* (objectives of *Shari'ah*) (Soualhi, 2008). Fundamentally, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* reveals the dignified view of Islam which has to be observed entirely, not partially, as Islam is an absolute and integrated pattern of life and its purpose includes the complete life, personal and public; in this world and the Hereafter (Ibn Ashur, 2006; Kamali, 1998). Therefore, a profound perception of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* involves serious obligation of each individual and organization to justice and social welfare. The outcome of such profound perception would be society where every individual (or group) will work together with each other rather than compete, as proper achievement in this life is to obtain the ultimate happiness (*falah*) (see Kamali, 2008a). Accordingly, barely maximization of profits cannot be *the only* driving goal of a Muslim society. Maximization of profit must go hand-in-hand with attempts to ensure healthy human awareness, justice, and fair play at all levels of human interaction (*mu'amalah*). Islamic finance in particular and Islamic economics in general are supposed to be based on the *maslahah* prescribed by *maqasid al-Shari'ah*. Economic agents in an Islamic framework, "will seek *maslahah* instead of seeking utility in the conventional sense" (Khan, 2002, p. 63). Only development described above would be in compliance with the *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* (Siddiqi, 2006).

¹ For detailed discussion about the development of Islamic finance industry in general see ISRA (2011), especially Chapter 4.

Maqasid al-Shari'ah should be underlined as one of the most imperative pillars for enhanced improvement of the financial structure. In addition to the *Shari'ah* set of laws and the regulations, it could be certainly said that *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* is the most complete mechanism to improve and add value to the current Islamic finance nowadays. However, comprehension of the concept of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* and its underlying principles is vital before applying it in the existing financial scenario. It is decisive to realize that public interest (*maslahah*) is the heart of the theory of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* itself. Hence, the general objective of *Shari'ah* is to preserve the society order of the community and ensure the continuity of its healthy progress. Allah (s.w.t.) says: "...I wish not, in contradiction to you, to do that which I forbid you. I only desire reform so far as I am able, to the best of My power, and My guidance cannot come except from Allâh, in Him I trust and unto Him I repent." (Al-Qur'an, Al-Hud: 88)

This paper studies the meaning, contemplation and appropriate application of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in Islamic finance. It elaborates the ways of realizing the dignified objectives of *Shari'ah* in all sectors of Islamic finance. These objectives are elaborated in various and different aspects such as the appropriate meaning and significance of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*; the proper comprehension of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in Islamic finance; the role of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in prohibition of *riba* in contemporary Islamic Finance; the methods of implementing *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in Islamic banking; challenges of realizing *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in Islamic capital markets (*sukuk*); and application of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in *takaful*. The paper analyses all these applications and provides examples from the current practices of Islamic finance.

2.0 THEORY OF MAQASID AL-SHARI'AH

In recent years, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* received an increasing attention. However, its emphasis within the Islamic finance industry needs to be indoctrinated into all spheres of the industry and all parties involved need to take proactive role in implementing it on a much wider scale. When people discuss about the underlying principle(s) and justification of particular action in Islam, for example forbiddance of interest (*riba*) or obligation of payment of *zakah*, the majority of the answers to the coherent rationalizations are presented by *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*

(Lahsasna & Sulaiman, 2010). Every judgment comes with a reason. In case of the payment of *zakah*, the main objective is to purify one's wealth and the central justification for it is equal allocation of wealth to everyone. Consequently, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* reveals the noble vision of Islam which must be observed entirely as Islam is an absolute and integrated way of life. In general, its goal embraces both individuals and societies for the good in this world and the Hereafter. It underlines benefits for both of them and its laws are devised to shelter these benefits and support progress and rightness of the setting of human beings on earth (Soualhi, 2008). The Holy Qur'an illustrates this notably when it underlines the leading rationale for sending the Prophet Muhammad (s.a.w.s.) in verse: "*We sent Thee not, but as a Mercy for all creatures*" (*Al-Qur'an*, Al-Anbiya': 107). Furthermore, it can be also observed in the Qur'an's description of itself when it says "*O mankind! there hath come to you a direction from your Lord and a healing for the (diseases) In your hearts, - and for those who believe, a guidance and a mercy.*" (*Al-Qur'an*, Yunus: 57).

2.1 Definition of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*

The word "*Maqsid*" (plural: *Maqasid*) reflects a meaning of purpose, objective, principle, intent, goal (Kamali, 2008a; Lane, 1968).² *Maqasid* comprise the wisdom and knowledge behind rulings, the objectives of particular actions. As for the term "*Shari'ah*", some scholars define the word as following strictly the injunctions of Allah or the way of Islam (*din*) (Dusuki & Abdullah, 2007).³ Hence, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* represents "the objectives and the rationale of the Shari'ah" (Dusuki & Bouheraoua, 2011). It encompasses all disciplines, laws, regulations, policies, instructions, obligations, principles, beliefs, devotion and actions designed to protect the interest of human beings in all segments and aspects of life.

Various scholars have tried to elucidate the purposes and the objectives of *Shari'ah* upon which it is established. Among these the exceptional individuals are the Malikite Abu Ishaq al-Shatibi, the Shafite al-'Izz ibn 'Abd al-Salam, and the Hanbalite Ibn Qayyim al Jawziyyah (Lahsasna, 2009).

² "*Maqsid*" refers to "A place to, or towards, which one tends, repairs, or betakes himself; to which one directs his course; at which one aims; which one seeks, pursues, endeavours to reach, desires, or wishes for; [pl. مقاصد]" See Lane (1968, p. 2532).

³ Literally, *Shari'ah* means a path to a watering-place, a clear path to be followed. This led to its use for the path which the believer has to tread in order to obtain guidance in this world and deliverance in the next.

According to Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyyah (d. 1356), Shari'ah aims at safeguarding people's interest in this world and the Hereafter (Ibn Qayyim, n.d., p. 1; see also Kamali, 2008b, p. 27). Referring to the *maqasid al-Shari'ah*, al-Ghazali said: "The objective of the Shari'ah is to promote the welfare of human beings, which lies in safeguarding their faith, their life, their intellect, their posterity, and their wealth. Whatever ensures the safeguard of these five fundamentals serves public interest and is desirable" (Al-Ghazali, 1356/1937, pp. 139-140; see also Chapra, 1998; Chapra, 2008). Al-Shatibi approves al-Ghazali's list and sequence, hereby indicating that they are the most preferable in terms of their harmony with essence of *Shari'ah* (Ibn Ashur, 2006). Finally, Ibn Ashur (2006) provides a broader definition stating that:⁴

Both its general rules and specific proofs indicate that the all-purpose principle (*maqсад 'amm*) of Islamic legislation is to preserve the social order of the community and insure its healthy progress by promoting the well-being and righteousness (*salah*) of that which prevails in it, namely, the human species. The well-being and virtue of human beings consist of the soundness of their intellect, the righteousness of their deeds as well as the goodness of the things of the world where they live that are put at their disposal. (Ibn Ashur, 2006, p. 87)

2.2 *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*: An Overview

Maqasid al-Shari'ah calls for establishment of justice, elimination of unfairness and alleviation of privation. It endorses relationship and mutual support within the family and community in general (Dusuki, 2009a; Dusuki & Abozaid, 2007b; Dusuki & Bouheraoua, 2011). This has for outcome a preservation of public interest (*maslahah*) as the most important objective of the *Shari'ah*. *Shari'ah* recognizes three areas which constitute well-being, namely, endorsing benefits (*maslahah*) to people, educating individual and establishing justice (Mohamed & Dzuljastri, 2008).

One of the objectives and the underlying principle of the *Shari'ah* is endorsing benefits (*maslahah*) to the people. It is associated with people livelihood in this world and the Hereafter. Furthermore, it also aspires to avert people against wrongdoings, such as

⁴ For more definitions of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* see also Dusuki and Bouheraoua (2011).

corruption, theft and injustice. This implication can be seen in the following Qur'anic verse: “... and establish regular prayer: for prayer restrains from shameful and unjust deeds; and remembrance of Allah is the greatest (thing In life) without doubt. and Allah knows the (Deeds) that ye do.” (Al- Qur'an, Al-Ankabut: 45).

Every verdict in *Shari'ah* appears with reasoning and with a purpose, which is to shelter and protect public interests (*maslahah*) in all aspects and segments of life. It should also be observed that in specific occasions emergence of arguments between endorsement of benefit and avoidance of evil arise. If none appears to be preferable, then avoidance of evil takes precedence over the recognition of benefit (Chapra, 2008; Hasanuzzaman, 1998; Lahsasna & Sulaiman, 2010).

Educating individuals is an essential objective of *Shari'ah*, too. Education encourages people with faith and *Taqwa* (consciousness of Allah s.w.t.) in order to accomplish public objectives. A truthful and moral person can emerge as representative of others and bearer of the ruling of *Shari'ah* related to *ibadah*, *mu'amalah* and *jinayah* (Lahsasna & Sulaiman, 2010; Mohamed, 2006).

Lastly, one of the objectives of the *Shari'ah* is to maintain the standards of justice (*'adl*). It must be based on creation of equilibrium which accomplishes rights and responsibilities on one side, and abolishes unfairness and inequality on the other. It must embrace both individual and social justice, regardless whether it is a case of friend or foe, Muslim or non-Muslim, personal or public. Illicit behaviors and wrongdoings are disapproved and punished in order to avoid injustice as it is undesirable and contradictory with the philosophy of Qur'an and the *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* (Lahsasna & Sulaiman, 2010; Mohamed, 2007).

2.3 Classification of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*

Although there are different classifications of *maqasid al-Shari'ah*, Muslim scholars generally classified them into three main categories: *daruriyyat* (essentials), *hajiyyat* (needs) and *tahsiniyyat* (embellishments).⁵ *Maslahah*, according to *'ulama*, refers to “the

⁵ For detailed discussion on different classifications see Ibn Ashur (2006, pp. 112-129), Kamali (1998; 2008b, p. 134). See also Dusuki and Bouheraoua (2011).

preservation of the objectives of Shari'ah," (Khan, 2002, p. 64) which is considered to be the main objective of the Shari'ah (Kamali, 1998, p. 1).

The essentials (*daruriyyat*) are particulars that are required and considered as vital for the founding of wellbeing in this world and the Hereafter. If society in some way neglects them, the outcome will be anarchy together with disorder of the functionality of the society which will result in total collapse. The essential *masālih* (plural of *maslahah*) or *daruriyyat* are further divided into five: (i) Preservation of faith/religion (*Din*); (ii) Preservation of the life (*Nafs*); (iii) Preservation of lineage/descendants/procreation (*Nasl*); (iv) Preservation of property (*Mal*); and (v) Preservation of intellect/reason (*'Aql*) (Al-Ghazali, 1356/1937; see also Ayub, 2007, pp. 22-25; Çizakça, 2007; Kamali, 1998, p. 2; Khan, 2002, p. 64).

The embracement of the mentioned values is obligatory to ensure normal functioning of society and welfare of individuals. It is an obligation of society and people to implement all necessary measures to prevent or eliminate all the barriers that will hinder the realization of these values. The *Shari'ah* constantly seeks to embrace and endorse these values and enhance procedures for their continuation and progression. Furthermore, Islam as religion is greatly concerned with eradication of poverty and hardship of individuals and community, which is in consistency with the aims of *Shari'ah*. This is to ensure that people have prosperous life and that there will be no disruption to their normal life.

The needs (*hajiyyat*) serve as complementary to the essentials. Without the needs, people will face hardship. However, non-existence of the needs will not create complete disruption of the normal order of life as is the case with the essentials (Dusuki & Bouheraoua, 2011; Lahsasna & Sulaiman, 2010; Nyazee, 2002). Ibn Ashur (2006) defined the meaning of complementary necessities in the following manner: "It consists of what is needed by the community for the achievement of its interest and the proper functioning of its affairs. If it is neglected, the social order will not actually collapse but will not function well. Likewise, it is not on the level of what is indispensable (*daruri*) (Ibn Ashur, 2006, p. 123).

The embellishments (*tahsiniyyat*) relate to matters which bestow enhancement in the society and guide to improved life. The admirable illustrations are *Shari'ah's* guidelines as clean body and attire for purpose of prayer, offering charity and avoiding lavishness and

recommendation of supererogatory prayers (*'ibadat*). The rationale of all these are the accomplishment of integrity and perfection in entire fields of a person's behavior. However, without these values the society will still be able to function and normal life process will not be interrupted. The illustrations of these matters are: voluntary (*sadaqah*), and ethical and moral rules, and others (Dusuki & Bouheraoua, 2011; Ibn Ashur, 2006; Lahsasna & Sulaiman, 2010).

3.0 MAQASID AL-SHARI'AH AND ISLAMIC FINANCE

The significance of the *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in Islamic finance originates from the perspective of the wealth in Islamic law. This significance relates also to the objectives of the Islamic law in finance and business transactions and to the overall goals of *Shari'ah* in wealth (Lahsasna, 2009).

The protection and preservation of the wealth is categorized in the sphere of necessary matters (*daruriyyat*). In previous section it has been elaborated that essentials necessities are those which, without their preservation, there would be disorder and anarchy in society. The abolishment of preservation for these matters would have for result loss of everything that we embrace as valued (Ibn Ashur, 2006). This characterization and classification of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* demonstrates the most important position of the wealth and the substance of the finance in Islamic law. Therefore, it must be highlighted here that the finance is recognized by *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* as valuable aspect of life. Furthermore, the finance is preserved by Islamic law in form of Islamic lawful decisions and guidelines.

It is essentially important to stress on the realization of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in the current Islamic finance transactions because of the several important reasons. First, there is a strong relationship between the objectives of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* and the objectives of business transactions, as can be observed from the position of the wealth within Islamic law and *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* that requests the preservation of wealth in everyday business activities and the promotion of socially responsible activities. As a result, if objectives of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in business transactions are neglected, it may result in poverty and anarchy. Second, the business transactions in domestic and international trade should be based on the principles of Islamic law, and the fundamental objectives of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in finance

and business shall be applied as core guidelines to implement all types of financial transactions. Third, the particular objectives of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in business transactions must have perpetuity and constant outlook of the universal objectives of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*. Last but not the least, the regulations of business transactions should be within the rules and the requirements of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* and Islamic law. In other words, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* must administer and regulate the *Shari'ah* principle of the Islamic finance (Lahsasna, 2009; Lahsasna & Sulaiman, 2010).

3.1 *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah* in the prohibition of interest (*riba*)

From financial point of view, one of the most important objectives in *Shari'ah* is elimination of interest (*riba*) in all categories of business transactions. The two main categories of interest (*riba*) which are sternly prohibited in Islamic law are *riba al-nasiah*, which is interest on lent money, and *riba al-fadl* which is literally earnings or excess acquired by exchanging or selling commodities of superior value over other commodities given (Kahf, 2006). The Holy Quran states: “*those who devour usury will not stand except as stand one whom the evil one by His touch hath driven to madness. That is because they say: "Trade is like usury," but Allah hath permitted trade and forbidden usury (riba)*” (*Al-Qur'an*, Al-Baqarah: 275).

According to *Shari'ah*, both types of *riba* cause unfairness in business transaction. It generally provides rich individuals easy way to grow their wealth by weakening the other member of community. The *Shari'ah* categorized this type of profit as illegal earnings which are strictly disallowed. Looking from the society (*maslahah*) point of view *riba* makes the community indolent, unproductive and lowers individuals' contributions to the society. As a result, all banks and financial institutions must diverge from *riba* and perform wholesome business transactions excluding *riba*. It is an extremely challenging task; however it is a devoting responsibility and most important obligation of *Shari'ah* in order to enhance supreme Islamic products in banking and finance. In this sense, it can be further elaborated that the distinction between the Islamic banks and the conventional banks lays in the fact that the Islamic banks, being *Shari'ah*-compliant, in all business procedures disallow *riba*, whereas the conventional banks engage in all form of transactions without considering the illicit nature of *riba*. Therefore, the Islamic banks assess product from several perspectives,

including value of the transaction, profit and return, as well as the nature of the products. On the other hand, conventional bank evaluates the product from side of interest and profit only, without taking into consideration the condition of the religion in particular transaction (Mohamed, 2006).

3.2 *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in Islamic Banking

The previous sections discussed the fundamental principles of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* with focus on ordinary dealings of individuals as well as essence of *Maqasid* in Islamic Finance including view on interest (*riba*). This section further elaborates the importance of the *Shari'ah* matters with emphasis on *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* and *maslahah* in Islamic banking.

One of the most important issues in Islamic banking business today is to develop products and services that are *Shari'ah*-compliant or genuine from Islamic viewpoint without reducing the importance of the business features of being competitive, profitable and viable in the long run. However, there are several issues that should be addressed and one of the most pressing is what should be the foundation in justifying whether a product is *Shari'ah*-compliant or not? What are the genuine methods in *fiqh* when resolving whether a contract is legal and allowed from *Shari'ah* perspectives? In other words, the issue of form versus substance comes into picture here. *Fiqhi* scholars have diverged opinions on the concern of establishing the base of contract legality. Some stress on its permissible structure while others underline on its matter and the objectives of contracting sides.

This divergence of opinions could be linked to the following *hadith* that is used by the scholars to justify their positions, namely “*matters are determined by intention.*”⁶ Based on this *hadith*, legality of all contracts must be established by intention (*niyyah*). It is the rationale or matter of the contract, not mere looking at its structure or formation alone. However, some scholars like Imam Shafi stated that it is unreasonable to decide on the legality of contracts by implication of intention, as it is complex and sometimes improbable to categorize the intention of the contracting parties (Dusuki, 2007; Dusuki & Abozaid, 2007b; see also Hasanuzzaman, 1998). In addition, they stated that some *Shari'ah* texts indicate that evaluating things must be based on their structure and manifestation.

⁶ Narrated by ‘Umar al-Khattab, recorded by Al-Bukhari, *Sahih Al-Bukhari*.

To reconcile between these two conflicting texts in a practical way, scholars distinguished between two types of *hukm* (ruling): *hukm Qada'i* and *hukm Diani*. The former concerns with contract that complies with all *Shari'ah* conditions and requirements pertaining to a contract in its form and structure, while the later concerns with compliance of the substance or contract purpose which must be in line with the *Shari'ah*. If the contract structure is *Shari'ah* compliant, then it could be termed as a valid contract (*sahih*). On the other hand if the contractors' purpose of the contract is *Shari'ah* compliant, then it is permissible (*halal*). Thus, a transaction is deemed to be *halal* when it serves the legal purpose and intention, and *sahih* if the contract meets all contractual conditions and requirements. Consequently, a *sahih* (valid) contract is not necessarily *halal* (permissible). (Dusuki & Abozaid, 2007a, p. 16)

Therefore, a contract is considered permissible when it embraces the lawful rationale and intention, and legal if the contract contains all contractual settings and requirements. As a result, a legal contract is not always permissible (Dusuki & Abozaid, 2007a, 2007b; Ismail & Tohirin, 2010). It must be stated here that the scholars of *Fiqh* have different views with regard to the validity of a contract only. However, they have no issue with the permissibility of a contract on its matter or the contracting parties' *niyyah*. Even Shafi scholars expressed examples of cases when real intention does nullify a contract such as selling fruit products to be used for alcohol making or furnishing arms to people who will use it against the Muslims. This indicates that the importance on the structure or expressed intention is more appropriate when the genuine intention is hard to establish (Dusuki, 2009b).

The preceding elaboration has indicated that jurists are commonly in consent that for an Islamic financial product to be classified as *Shari'ah*-compliant, the contract must be both legal and permissible. However, based on discussion, a concern could be raised whether the contemporary Islamic banking products are certainly following the same principles. One of the most debatable products of Islamic banking is buy-back sale (*bay' al-'inah*) which is mostly applied in Malaysia. In *bay' al-'inah* approach the Islamic bank is theoretically acting as a trader selling or buying as the word "*bay'*" advocate, but in actual terms the Islamic bank simply proceeds as a financier who provides capital without exposing itself to any risk and

without taking engagement in the venture procedure. *Bay' al-'inah* here is resorted to as a legal device to avoid *riba* based loan. However, financing based on *bay' al-'inah* and the conventional *riba* based loan are very similar; they satisfied closely the same contracting parties' purposes, and apply exactly the same economic matter and outcomes, although their form may be different (Dusuki & Abozaid, 2007b).

Thus, it can be seen that some products offered by Islamic banks are not enhancing *maslahah* or in other words not fully embracing the objective of *Shari'ah*. Islamic banks relatively put focus more on the form rather than substance itself as an effort to fulfil compliance with *Shari'ah*. If embracing *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* involves observing the underlying principle of the texts, subsequently, observing only the structure and the formation of the contracts will be in opposition to the key principles of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*. In this case, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* has been used as a rationalization for application of rather questionable transaction, even though observing *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* must be the first factor to determine their prohibition (Dusuki, 2007).

It is important to note that the conception of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* not only embrace individually entitled goals but also involve broader procedures sheltering welfare in order to achieve justice and equity. Islamic banking must take into consideration the universal and dynamic conception of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*. Banks must develop its role by embracing social objective, not only an individual objective. The dignified vision to endorse social welfare of the society is related to development of a wellbeing economics oriented model where social righteousness and principle rules can be implemented (Kamal, Yusof, & Kashoogie, 2009). Thus, Islamic banks are expected to engage in endorsing social welfare. This view is embraced by the various Muslim scholars who are stating that Islamic banking is much more than providing *Shari'ah*-compliant products. It should be structured in such a way that its primarily goal is to achieve an affirmative contribution to the realization of the socio economic objectives of the society at large (Mohamed, 2007).

In order to accomplish the social welfare of society or economic wellbeing model supported by those Muslim scholars, Islamic banks should rely more on equity-based financing.⁷ The equity financing is the way forward for realizing that stage of model as preserved in *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* (Haneef & Smolo, 2010; Rosly, 2010; Usmani, 2010). As a result, equity financing is an aspiration of *Shari'ah* advisors as well as academicians that has to be enhanced further in the Islamic banking. Furthermore, equity-based financing is also not disguise of debt-based financing contracts commonly used in the conventional banking. Therefore, it can be freely uttered that equity financing can accomplish the objective of *Shari'ah* which is realization of justice in the society (Kamal, et al., 2009).

3.3 *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah* in Islamic Capital Markets (*Sukuk*)

During the last couple of decades Islamic financial industry has developed and reached significant results. It has found a variety of financial and business establishments, and widened its scope from only banking industry to areas which integrate capital market products and services. Nowadays, Islamic capital market like conventional is a noteworthy factor of the general Islamic financial scheme. It plays a vital role in allocation of funds, from surplus unit (savers), to deficit unit (borrowers) in daily activities. Furthermore, the Islamic capital market basically furnishes an enormous section of liquidity to the large number of illiquid assets. This is realized by providing a broad spectrum of products assorted from *Shari'ah*-compliant securities to bond-like formation known as *sukuk*. As a result, one of the most important accomplishments of Islamic capital market is in the rise of *sukuk* market worldwide. The enhanced application of *sukuk* in recent years comes from the need of governments and corporations to reach funds from the Islamic capital markets through a *sukuk* issuance. However, the techniques and processes employed to develop and configure the *sukuk* must comply with *Shari'ah* values and principles. The principles which are presented within the spectrum of *Shari'ah* are uttered not only through its transactions but in the extent of its comprehending the *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*.

⁷ This, however, does not mean that the debt-based financing should be abolished altogether. Rather, what is meant here is that the use of the debt-based financing should be minimized and only for essential (*daruriyyat*) purposes. For detailed discussion about the debt-based financing and its role within Islamic finance, as well as, how to approach this issue see Haneef and Smolo (2010).

Despite continuous improvements in the field of Islamic capital market through a range of *Shari'ah*-compliant product innovations like *sukuk*, some products - which tried to mimic conventional bonds - misrepresent the *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*. This misrepresentation arose from the poor comprehension of *Shari'ah*, by only taking into consideration the lawful structure of a contract rather than focusing on the substance as well when configuring a financial product.

The best example of financial product which, somehow, overlooks *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in Islamic capital markets could be seen in equity-based *sukuk*. The crucial uniqueness of equity-based *sukuk*, from *Shari'ah* viewpoint, lies in their two essential attributes: (i) the capital cannot be guaranteed; and (ii) the periodic returns are also dependent on real profits made and can be uneven (Dusuki, 2009b). However, the firm *Shari'ah* directions related to the equity-based *sukuk* structure are usually not of great interest to conventional risk adverse investors. Particularly, the incorporation of classical Islamic financial instruments like *mudarabah* and *musharakah* with bond do not fulfill conventional investors' requests. One of the reasons could be their "greedy" prospect of capital protection and fixed income instruments, which are usual characteristics of conventional bond instruments. Eventually, the structure of equity-based *sukuk* has changed into debt-based (mimicking conventional bond) instruments. Furthermore, different "conventional credit approaches" were also integrated to the *mudarabah* and *musharakah sukuk* configuration to realize capital protection and predict possible returns alike fixed income or bonds instruments (Dusuki, 2010; Dusuki & Mokhtar, 2010; Mokhtar, 2011). These "conventional approaches" furnished fixed income and capital protection aspects to the equity-based *sukuk* as well as embraced the conventional bond characteristics. Consequently, investors were able to attain the same financial outcomes as if they invest in conventional bonds.

Nevertheless, these fixed-income embracing instruments entrenched into equity-based *sukuk* had been the theme of strong condemnation by different parties in terms of their compliance with the *Shari'ah* requirements. Above all, *Shari'ah* Board of Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) printed a testimonial in February 2008 signifying that *musharakah* and *mudarabah sukuk* with the "credit enhancement

approach” instruments as applied by the market was not in accordance with the *Shari’ah* principles (AAOIFI, 2008).

Looking into details, the AAOIFI’s proclamation underlined two core matters observed in equity-based *sukuk*: First, the practice of liquidity facility; and second, the purchase undertaking at par to redeem the *sukuk*. In fact, AAOIFI restated its present regulation on investment *sukuk* particularly on the practice of liquidity facility and the purchase undertaking at par (AAOIFI, 2008).

Viewed from purely *Shari’ah* perspective, *sukuk* that are based on *mudarabah* or *musharakah* should not incorporate any structure of security for either the return or the principal as it is observed in a mortgage bond that has solid equity attributes. Furthermore, most of the equity-based *sukuk* are based either on the sale of asset with a promise to repurchase the assets by the *Sukuk* manager (obligor promise principle), or *sukuk* holders infuse capital into the business process of the *Sukuk* manager (Dusuki, 2010; Mokhtar, 2011). In *mudarabah*, the obligor does not need to participate with any asset while in *musharakah*, the obligor will furnish capital. For all mentioned instruments there will be promise by the obligor to repurchase the assets from *sukuk* holders, for its nominal value at a specific agreed price. This would guarantee that the capital invested by the *sukuk* holders remains integral (Dusuki, 2009b). However, this may lead to the same economic results as conventional bonds since *sukuk* holders shall be assured that their capital will be guaranteed at maturity due to the purchase undertaking that allows *sukuk* assets to be redeemed at par.

Nevertheless, the “credit enhancement approach” embraces arrangements and commitments, which, if taken on their own, are acceptable and permissible. The “innovative” permissibility of such arrangements and commitments is the main reason why these structures and arrangements had received concern by the *Shari’ah* jurists. If looked carefully, the total procedure of *sukuk* issuance, these annual allocation payments and claims of value upon maturity, these obvious promises and undertakings clearly reflect capital protection and assured rate of return on investment, what is actually conventional bond characteristic, and which would be impossible to achieve in pure *Shari’ah* based instruments like the *mudarabah* and *musharakah* contracts (Dusuki, 2010).

As a result, the question is whether such practices are used as deception to avoid particular unlawful instruments by embracing lawful ways and provisions? However, as elaborated previously, the lawful structure is not enough to confirm and rationalize the permissibility of a contract even though it may be legal. Accordingly, to declare a financial instrument permissible based only on the legal structure of the transaction will certainly raise some concerns over its legality and stand in opposition to the basic principles of *Shari'ah*. The use of “credit approach” strategy like purchase undertaking in structuring *sukuk* to enable guarantee-resemblance features of conventional bonds obviously have maintained the legality of the form (*sahih qada'an*) but neglected the legality of the substance (*sahih diyanatan*) (Dusuki, 2009b). If embracing *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* logically endows embracing the foundations of the texts then observing only the structure of the contracts goes against the very fundamentals of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* from the contract. Actually, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* have been applied here as a rationalization for doubtfully legal transactions, even though observing *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* must be the primary aspect to agree on its prohibition.

3.4 *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah* and *Takaful*

Takaful is a structure based on unity, harmony of psyche and shared protection which offers joint financial and other forms of support to members of the society in case of explicit need, whereby members jointly consent to give money to uphold this universal objective (Abdul Wahab, Lewis, & Hassan, 2007). The central idea of *takaful* is to spread the risk among the members. The core distinction between conventional insurance and *takaful* is that in conventional insurance the risk is conveyed to the insurer while in *takaful* the risk is shared jointly by the members of the *takaful* fund under the *takaful* scheme (Kwon, 2007).

Takaful can be observed as a system of joint assurance among members against loss and damage that may be imposed upon any of them. The participants of the group consent to pledge mutually that if any of them suffer a calamity, he will be given a certain amount of money to meet the loss and damage.

As explained by Mortuza (2006), “*Takaful* is based on the concept of cooperation, brotherhood and solidarity of the members of the society who voluntarily agree to contribute

money to support a common goal of providing mutual financial aid to the members of the group under certain terms and conditions.”

Pursuing an Islamic life insurance policy does not mean that one has insured one’s own life, but it is a righteous financial transaction created for the reimbursement of particular weak individuals in the society (Abdul Wahab, et al., 2007). According to Ahmed Zia, “It is obligatory that the society should be protected by offering security against “risk” for all individual making the fund-pooling foundation. In the lack of such a security, everyone will endure from the uncertainties and apprehension” (Ahmed, 2010b). A provision of such a security is likely when there is fairness, righteousness and economics stability in society (*maslahah*). In case of *Takaful*, every individual stays under the security or surety-ship (*kafalah*) of the group. In practical term, *takaful* will provide protection to all businessmen and persons in the society against the divine and material losses. In primordial civilization, group lived together in form of families or tribe, where their wants were entirely fulfilled and sheltered, through joint collaboration and mutual assistance (see Dusuki, 2006). As a result, they were relatively protected against all types of loses. It was the previous technique of insurance (Abdulaziz, 2010).

This said, it could be observed that main *takaful* application is very similar, i.e. to enhance social cohesion, facilitate protection of the society from the harmful impact of unpleasant conditions, raise value of life through the composure that comes from safety, and accumulate and endow money through a joint scheme that allocates profit on payments (subscriptions) invested by policyholders on annual basis (Maysami & Williams, 2006). The essential basics which are emphasizing *Takaful* theory are identical to joint and shared principles, to the degree that the theory of cooperation and sharing is one that is endowed under Islamic Law. Apart from instructing humankind to believe in Allah (s.w.t.), the Divine Decree, the Will of Allah (s.w.t.) and the Prophet Mohammad (s.a.w.s.), the Holy Qur’an, among others noble deeds, encourages the individuals to help each other and to embrace vigilance in order to reduce hardship, losses or wrongdoings from adverse actions (Yaquby, 2000). As could be seen, in origins of *takaful* the essential references of sharing and mutuality were solely the Holy Qur’an and the *Hadith*. However, *takaful*, as it is applied nowadays, is rather based on

the secondary source of Islamic jurisprudence – *Ijtihad*⁸ (Abdulaziz, 2010). Nevertheless, the basis of the *takaful* system remained unchanged, i.e. not to profit but to uphold the principle of "bear ye one another's burden" (Ahmed, 2010a).

Therefore, the distinguishing aspect of Islamic insurance is that it is not solely profit-motivated; essential purpose is self-help through cooperation. It advanced as a collective institution with objective to amortize the burden of an individual by splitting it among his fellow members. From a conventional perspective, insurance emerges as set of mutual contracts that transfer risk for the benefit of the individuals who choose to make that contract (Kwon, 2007). On the other hand, from an Islamic perspective, insurance appears as a foundation that amortizes or removes risk for the benefit of a social group (*maslahah*). This is based on the principles of co-operation as mentioned in a Qur'anic verse in *Surah al-Ma'idah*: "help ye one another in righteousness and piety, but help ye not one another in sin and rancour..." (Al-Qur'an, Al-Ma'idah: 2).

Finally, as mentioned already earlier, all economic activities including the fundamental principles governing contracts in general must conform to the *Shari'ah*. Accordingly, the subject matter of the contract should be lawful; the intended objectives of the contract should be in line with the principles of the *Shari'ah*; the contract should be free from the interest (*riba*), gambling (*maysir*), fraud, coercion and high degree of uncertainty (*gharar*); the participants to the contract should agree to co-operate actively for their common good; every participant pays a contribution in order to help those who need assistance; and the contract should not aim at deriving undue advantage for one participant at the expense of the other participants (Mansuri, 2006, pp. 5-23).

4.0 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Islamic financial system has potentials to become the envoy for the implementation of the righteous objectives of *Shari'ah*, as it resides within a financial path underlined by the nature of *Shari'ah* rulings. These *Shari'ah* rulings correlate Islamic financial transactions with real

⁸ The word *Ijtihad* refers to the practice of making a verdict by independent understanding of the legal sources, the Holy Qur'an and the *Sunnah*.

concern for just, fair and transparent society. Concurrently, *Shari'ah* rulings prohibit involvement in forbidden activities which are harmful to social and environmental welfare.

Maqasid al-Shari'ah is seeking to develop Islamic finance on firm grounds which can accept all improvement in financial transactions, whether it is related to the banking system, capital market, or *takaful* industry. This firm position and prominent basis will help the Islamic finance to achieve a better performance. It could be strongly affirmed that *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* is the best elucidation for Islamic finance, particularly by looking into observation that the Islam itself is absolute system for living in all aspects including business and finance. From the firm ground of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah*, Muslim jurists and scholars, through the growth of the business transactions and finance, have introduced a number of *Shari'ah* principles in order to regulate and rule financial transactions. These principles should be implemented by Islamic banks and financial institutions in all aspects of finance. At the same time, this is to guarantee the consistency of the business and to smooth the progress of achieving *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* in financial transactions.

Finally, limited views of understanding *Shari'ah*, by only highlighting on the lawful forms of a contract, needs to be amended. Instead, the matter that has greater implications to the implementation of *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* must be observed, in particular when structuring a financial product. Therefore, Islamic finance must make sure that all of its transactions are *Shari'ah*-compliant not only in its forms and lawful procedures but more significantly in its substance and economic matters which are premised on the objectives outlined by *Shari'ah*.

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